

WIND VALUE

An Opportunity for Climate Action and for Energy Communities

End of Life Decisions for Wind Farms:
An Opportunity for Climate Action and for Energy Communities

Report: Summer Research Seminar
Work Package 7

Month 39/48, May 2025

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 Taighde Éireann
Research Ireland

Wind Value Funding Ref: IRC*21/PATH-A/9348 Peter Deeney SFI-IRC Pathway Prog
July 1, 2025

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The Wind Value project is based in the Sustainability Institute of University College Cork (UCC), Ireland. The PI, Peter Deeney, may be found at the Cleaner Production Promotion Unit, G0.3, Ellen Hutchins Building, Lee Road, Cork T23 X10. The Research Team comprises: Luca Bernardi, Kevin Campbell, Peter Deeney, Claire Ducourtieux, Niall Dunphy, Fabian Gogolin, Paul Leahy, Benoit Mayol, Dorcas Allan Mikindani, John O'Brien and Rebecca Windemer. **The DOI for this report is 10.5281/zenodo.15786342.**

Suggested Citation: Deeney, P. (2025) Report: Summer Research Seminar, Cork, Ireland, Zenodo, <https://zenodo.org/records/15786342>, Accessed (date).

Executive Summary

This research project seeks to estimate a financial valuation for onshore wind farms in Ireland with particular application to investment risk. It will develop decision support tools which will assist wind farm managers to decide between decommissioning, repowering and life-extension for the end-of-life of a wind farm. This research will also assist local communities who may be interested in buying part or all of their local wind farm.

The Summer Research Seminar allowed a range of research projects across the UCC Sustainability Institute to share ideas and take advantage a networking opportunity. The Seminar was primarily a dissemination opportunity to share research results with students and staff from Juniata College. This will encourage future cooperation between these universities looking at energy planning, human decision making and the use of hydrogen to store wind energy and light energy.

Funding Acknowledgement

The Summer Research Seminar of the Wind Value research project is supported by [Research Ireland](#) under the Pathway Programme IRC*21/PATH-A/9348, awarded to Peter Deeney.

[Slides](#).

3.2 Implementing Human(e) Stakeholder Engagement in Energy Transitions

[Breffni Lennon](#) presented research about human perception of climate change and the need for a just energy transition. The presentation looks at the social and power structures not just the technical and physical aspects of renewable energy. [Slides](#), [Video](#).

3.3 Investor Risk for Onshore Wind Farms

[Peter Deeney](#) presented recent results concerning the risks for investors wishing to buy working wind farms as they approach their end of planning consent. The results are important for communities which may wish to take partial or whole ownership of their local wind farms. [Slides](#), [Audio](#).

3.4 Pathway to Green Hydrogen Fuel through Novel Materials, Water & Light

[Vittoria Anastasi](#) presented research from the [FreeHydroCells](#) group looking at methods to create hydrogen based fuel from solar energy and water. [Slides](#), [Audio](#).

4 Relevance for Wind Value

The event served the purposes of the Wind Value project in two ways:

- Disseminating results from Wind Value to a group of students and staff from a university in USA.
- Enabling researchers, students and academics to meet.
- Bringing together different strands of renewable energy research, in detail:
- Section [3.1](#) indicates where the electricity market is likely to go and how demand may increase.
- Section [3.2](#) is relevant to the critical issue of planning consent and social licence to operate, both of which are necessary for wind energy.
- Section [3.4](#) is important as the technology developed can use electricity or light energy to create hydrogen, and therefore offers a market for wind energy which is critical due to grid congestion.

5 Acknowledgments

The Wind Value project has received the bulk of its funding from [Research Ireland](#) under the Pathway Scheme for early career academics, reference number IRC*21/PATH-A/9348 Peter Deeney SFI-IRC Pathway Prog. Wind Value would like to thank Helen McMahon and Mitra Kamidivand of the [UCC Sustainability Institute](#) for assistance.

[CAPACITY](#) - Climate Action Pathways & Absorptive Capacity is supported by the [Department of Environment, Climate and Communications of the Irish Government](#).

[CLIMATUDE](#), Understanding Irish People's Attitudes, Beliefs and Values Related to Climate Change, is supported by [Ireland's Environmental Protection Agency](#).

[FreeHydroCells](#) is supported by the European Union.